

IMPORTANCE OF ELECTROLYSIS PROCESS IN INDUSTRY

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Abstract: the article describes the process of electrolysis, its application in industry, the processes of forming a protective coating on the surface of metals.

Key words: electrolyzer, cathode, anode, electrode, electroplating.

Аннотация: в статье описан процесс электролиза, его применение в промышленности, процессы формирования защитного покрытия на поверхности металлов.

Ключевые слова: электролизер, катод, анод, электрод, гальваника.

When an electric current passes through an electrolyte solution or solution, dissolved substances or other substances at the electrodes are produced as secondary reactions at the electrodes. This physical-chemical process is called electrolysis. The essence of electrolysis is that the ions in the electrolyte liquid move in an orderly manner in the electric field created by the electrodes. The negative electrode is the cathode, and the positive electrode is the anode. Negative ions called anions (hydroxyl group ions and anions of acid residues) move to the anode, and positive ions, cations (hydrogen, metals, ammonium, etc.) move to the cathode. An oxidation-reduction process takes place at the electrodes: the electrochemical reduction of particles (atoms, molecules, cations) occurs at the cathode, and the electrochemical oxidation of particles (atoms, molecules, anions) occurs at the anode.

Dissociation reactions in electrolyte solutions or liquids are called primary reactions, and reactions occurring directly at the electrodes are called secondary reactions. Separation of electrolysis reactions into primary and secondary reactions

helped Michael Faraday create the laws of electrolysis. Faraday's first law of electrolysis: during electrolysis, the mass of the substance released to the electrode is directly proportional to the amount of electricity supplied to this electrode. Electric quantity refers to electric charge, usually measured in coulombs. Faraday's second law of electrolysis: the mass of a chemical compound formed under the influence of a certain amount of electric current (electric charge) given to an electrode is directly proportional to its equivalent mass.

Formation of a protective coating is the process of formation of metal coatings on their surface when a direct electric current passes through solutions of metal and non-metal compounds, it is a field of applied electrochemistry. Forming a protective coating is the joining of another metal to the metal surface, which serves as the cathode of the electrolyzer and is firmly attached (adhered) to the metal (item) to be coated. Before coating the protective metal, it is necessary to clean the surface of the product from oil and other parts, otherwise the metal will be placed unevenly, and in addition, the adhesion (bonding) of the coating metal to the surface of the product will be of poor quality. Plating can be used to cover an object (metal) with a thin layer of gold or silver, chromium or nickel. The electrolysis process can be used to apply the best metal coatings to various metal surfaces. With this coating method, the part is used as a cathode placed in a metal salt solution, from which the coating should be removed. A plate made of the same metal is used as the anode. The process of obtaining clear, easily removable metal replicas (busts, statues, etc.) of various non-metallic and metallic objects of relatively large thickness by electrolysis, called electrotype matrices, is called electroplating.

Electroplating is one of the branches of galvanotechnology, which is the formation of a relief object from non-ferrous metal by deposition from a solution under the influence of electric current. It is used to obtain metal copies of objects by electrolysis. Protective plating is used to apply thick metal coatings to other metals (eg, to form a "patch" layer of nickel, silver, gold, etc.). In addition to the above, electrolysis is also used in other areas: metals on thin oxide protective films (layers) (anodization); electrochemical surface cleaning (polishing); water purification to remove soluble

impurities from it; industrial production of aluminum, fluorine, alkaline and alkaline earth metals, etc. The result is soft water (according to its characteristics, it is close to distilled); Electrochemical sharpening can be used to produce cutting tools (such as surgical knives, razors, etc.), chrome-plated, nickel-plated utensils and articles.

In the chemical industry, electrolysis is used to obtain valuable chemical products such as hydrogen and oxygen from water. Hydrogen obtained by electrolysis is used for thermal and cooling of generators in the energy industry. Chlorine and alkali are obtained by electrolysis from sodium chloride solution, and fluorine is obtained from solutions of its salts.

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